

Thin Layer Chromatography of Metal Ions Complexed with Anils. Part IV

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p-Dimethylamino and *p*-diethylamino anils of 3-benzoyl methyl glyoxal acting as bidentate ligands to form coloured chelates with some rare transition metals of 5d block have been used for their thin layer chromatographic detection and separation on silica gel layers. Quantitative estimations of mixtures have also been done spectrophotometrically by using elutes of chromatogram fragments.

IN continuation to our work¹⁻³ on thin layer chromatography (TLC) of transition metal-anil complexes present paper reports the rapid TLC detection, separation and determination of some rare transition metal ions, viz. Os(VIII), Ir(III), Pt(IV) and Au(III) and also explores a new analytical method for the trace analysis of these metals in diverse materials e.g. ores and minerals. The structural formulae of *p*-dimethylamino(A) and *p*-diethylamino (B) anils of 3-benzoyl methyl glyoxal, the chelating agents used in present studies are presented below.

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_2\text{CO}$ and $\text{R}' = \text{CH}_3$ or C_2H_5

Experimental

Glass plates (18×3 cm and 18×10 cm) were coated with silica gel free from iron and chloride ions and mixed with starch (E. Merck) as binder (19:1, w/w) to prepare layers of 0.1 cm thickness by usual method⁴. The coated plates were dried at ~100° for 2-4 hrs in an oven. Sample solutions were applied on the plates with fine capillaries. Dry plates were developed in glass chambers with ground-in-lids by the ascending technique. The time of development given in Table-1 is for distance 8-10 cms travelled by the solvent front. No locating agent was used because spots were self evident in day light.

Synthesis of ligands and Complexes and Physical measurements

The methods of preparations, composition and characteristics of both the chelating agents and their complexes⁶ (Table-1) have already been reported.

Stoichiometric studies of the complexes were made by employing refractometric and spectrophotometric techniques. For the refractometric and spectrophotometric measurements Abbe's refractometer and

'Spectronic-20' spectrophotometer (Bausch and Lomb) respectively were used.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometric investigations⁷ in the complexes under study have established 1:2 and 1:1 metal-ligand ratios in Os(VIII), Ir(III) and Pt(IV), Au(III) complexes respectively.

The R_F values of the complexes chromatographed individually using different solvents with silica gel adsorbent and starch binder are noted in Table-1. The R_F values of metal complexes after being complexed with each ligand present in solvent (0.02 gm/100 ml) have been found not appreciably different (~0.02) from the values reported in Table-1. These results explore the separation of mixture of all the four metal ions in BuOH (Aq)-CHCl₃ (6:4, v/v) mixture solvent with A. B ligand has been found less effective as it could resolve ternary mixture of Os(VIII), Pt(IV) and Au(III) complexes in BuOH(Aq)-CHCl₃ (1:1, v/v).

In the mixture analysis of Os(VIII), Ir(III), Pt(IV) and Au(III) ions their very dilute mixture solutions were used and 0.02 gm of A per 100 ml of solvent was added in the solvent. The R_F values of the chelates when their mixture was applied were also found unchanged from the values for each component if migrated from the individual point of application. The rates of migrations of the complexed species were quite different which evidently showed their separation. Different intense colours of chromatogram components were used in their identification.

The R_F values of the metal complexes vary with the layer thickness but are independent of plate size.

A perusal of TLC data also reveals that polarity of solvent has got an effective role in establishing R_F . High R_F values retained in less polar solvents.

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TABLE 1—SPOT-COLOUR, λ_{max} AND R_F OF COMPLEXES IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

Complex	Spot Colour	λ_{max} (nm)	MeCN	Me ₂ CO	BuOH	C ₆ H ₆	CHCl ₃	CCl ₄	Ag-BuOH 7:3	BuOH:C ₆ H ₆ (v/v) 1:1	Aq. BuOH 9:1	BuOH:CHCl ₃ (v/v) 4:1	BuOH:CHCl ₃ (v/v) 3:2	1:1	2:3	Acidic BuOH N/50	BuOH:CHCl ₃ Acid N/100	3:2 Acid N/200		
OsO ₂ A ₃ Cl ₄	Bluish pink	380	0.95	0.98	0.26	0.00	0.94	0.94	0.65	0.70	0.27	0.39	0.40	0.72	0.42	0.48	0.48	0.44		
IrA ₃ Cl ₄	pink	380	0.95	0.96	0.94	0.00	0.07	0.95	0.57	0.44	0.23	0.43	0.59	0.82	0.46	0.50	0.00	0.69		
PtCl ₄	Dark brown	500	0.94	0.94	0.95	0.00	0.10	0.95	0.00	0.26	0.30	0.33	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.43		
AuAlCl ₄	Brown	390	0.12	0.30	0.25	0.00	0.03	0.98	0.60	0.43	0.25	0.38	0.46	0.51	0.50	0.74	0.55	0.42		
OsO ₂ B ₂ Cl ₄	Light Blue	—	0.98	0.96	0.94	0.00	0.95	0.97	0.55	0.28	0.26	0.11	0.43	0.45	0.43	0.41	0.41	0.50		
IrB ₃ Cl ₄	Light pink	—	0.98	0.95	0.94	0.00	0.96	0.93	0.00	0.28	0.22	0.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		
PtCl ₄	Light brown	—	0.97	0.92	0.95	0.00	0.00	0.97	0.00	0.25	0.17	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.69	0.41	0.00		
AuCl ₄	Light brown	—	0.10	0.25	0.95	0.00	0.00	0.96	0.07	0.30	0.16	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.11	0.71	0.50	0.35		
Development time (minutes)			33	23	90	30	60	63	103	50	65	77	115	110	110	40	45	30	40	42

Room temperature=32±2°C

λ_{max} for A =370 nm

λ_{max} for B =370 nm

Quantitative Estimations :

Quantitative estimations of metal ions were made spectrophotometrically only complexing with A. The wave lengths (λ_{max}) at which ligand and complexes showed maximum absorption are noted in Table-1. At λ_{max} of each complex ligand showed negligible absorption and therefore subsequent spectrophotometric studies were carried out at λ_{max} of each chelate.

Fig. 1

Prior to the quantitative estimation of the mixture components the necessary amount of the reagent (A) required for the determination of each metal has been determined ; the optical density at λ_{max} (complex) of a series of solutions containing reagent and metal in the molar ratios from 1:1 to 9:1 were measured and curves were plotted between O.D. and moles of reagent added. Each curve showed an inflexion at the stoichiometric ratio of the respective complex beyond which they proceed linearly almost parallel to X-axis indicating that addition of any more reagent than stoichiometric amount would not make any considerable effect on the complex optical density.

The scrapped chromatogram fragments were eluted with acetonitrile and optical density of known volumes of elutes were determined at λ_{max} of complex component present. The concentration of corresponding metal in elute was deduced from a standard calibration curve prepared under similar conditions (Fig. 1). Limit of maximum separation has been found in ppm. as, Os(VIII), 5.5 ; Ir(III), 12.0 ; Pt(IV), 22.5 ; Au(III), 9.5.

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